

Evaluating Prestressed Concrete Beams with Cracks using Machine Learning

Mohamed Hassan Lasheen¹, Pinar Okumus², Negar Elhami Khorasani³, Varun Chandola⁴

¹Graduate Research Assistant, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, US

²Associate Professor, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, US

³Associate Professor, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, US

⁴Associate Professor, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, US

*Corresponding Author: Pinar Okumus, pinaroku@buffalo.edu

Abstract:

Bridge owners face challenging decisions on whether a bridge should be posted, repaired or replaced when prestressed concrete members have shear-related cracks due to overloading. The decisions are currently made based on engineering judgment, costly load-testing or time consuming and complex modeling. This project developed a reliable and efficient tool through machine learning to relate cracking to applied shear and stiffness of bridge members. The project also extended existing datasets by creating new high quality test data that can be used to validate the developed tool and to improve its predictions.

Two Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) algorithms were trained to correlate shear crack widths, beam geometric, material, and design properties with applied shear and stiffness of the beams. Two databases comprising of 79 and 37 beams were compiled for applied shear and stiffness predictions, respectively. The beams in the applied shear and stiffness databases have 409 and 254 data points related to crack widths, respectively. The GPR models achieved mean absolute percentage errors of 7% and 18% for the applied shear and stiffness predictions, respectively.

A Pennsylvania PA18/30 beam was designed as a test specimen. Pre-test predictions of shear strength were obtained from design codes. The beam was tested under quasi-static cyclic loading. The beam exhibited shear cracks and resisted loads higher than calculated by design codes. Residual and transient shear crack widths, along with concrete and steel strains and midspan displacements, were recorded at each loading cycle.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bridge owners face difficult decisions about whether to post, repair, or replace a bridge when prestressed concrete (PC) members develop shear cracks due to overloading. These decisions are currently based on engineering judgment, costly load testing, or time-consuming modeling. Clear guidance is needed to interpret cracking in order to avoid overly conservative load ratings while maintaining safety, economy, and bridge operability.

A machine learning (ML) based tool was developed to relate cracking to applied shear and stiffness of bridge members corresponding to crack widths. This web-based tool can be used by bridge owners, asset managers, and inspectors to inform repair decisions. A beam was tested to validate the ML-based tool and to increase its reliability.

2. APPLIED SHEAR AND STIFFNESS PREDICTIONS

Applied shear and stiffness corresponding to a crack width are important indicators of a beam's condition, providing insight into residual capacity and how structural behavior changes with cracking. Two beam test databases were compiled to train Gaussian Process regression (GPR) algorithms that correlate crack widths with their corresponding applied shear and stiffness.

2.1 Data Collection, Filtering, and Preprocessing

Test databases were compiled from the literature (Bruce 1962, Hanson and Hulsbos 1969, Moayer and Regan 1974, Bennett and Debaiky 1974, XuanI *et al.* 1988, Maruyama and Rizkalla 1988, Teoh *et al.* 2002, De Silva and Witchukreangkrai 2006, Heckmann and Bayrak 2008, Lee *et al.* 2010, De Wilder *et al.* 2015, Villamizar *et al.* 2017). Only slender, normal-weight concrete, simply supported beams that failed in shear and were prestressed with bonded strands were considered.

The first database was used to predict the applied shear and had 79 beams, providing 409 applied shear data points with their corresponding crack widths. The second database was a subset of the first database, was used to predict stiffness, and had beams that have both crack width records and load-midspan displacement relationship. The stiffness database consisted of 37 beams, providing 254 stiffness data points.

To obtain the stiffness, the load-displacement curves were smoothed and irregularities caused by pauses during testing were removed. In addition, the portions of the load-displacement curves after the peak load were excluded. Stiffness values were then sampled from the curves at eleven displacement intervals. The first interval extended from zero displacement to the end of the initial linear region. The remaining ten intervals were equally distributed between the end of the linear region and the displacement corresponding to the measured shear strength. Input and output features were scaled using z-score normalization and logarithmic scale, respectively, to prevent bias toward specific features (Juszczak *et al.* 2002, Wan 2019).

2.2 Selection of Predictive Features

Ten predictive features were selected to predict the applied shear and stiffness as follows: product of area of prestress and effective prestress, product of the area of longitudinal reinforcement and yield strength of this reinforcement, beam bottom flange width, distance between the extreme compression fiber and the centroid of prestressing strands at midspan, product of the area of shear reinforcement and yield strength of this reinforcement divided by shear reinforcement spacing, beam web width, square root of concrete compressive strength, ratio of shear span to distance between the extreme compression fiber and the

centroid of prestressing strands at midspan, product of the area of draped strands and the sine of draped strand angle, and shear crack width.

2.3 Postprocessing of Predictions

A post-processing constraint was applied to the applied shear predictions such that the predicted applied shear (V_{applied}) for a cracked beam cannot exceed the experimental shear strength (V_{max}). Two constraints were applied for stiffness: (1) when the crack width was zero, the predicted stiffness (K_{applied}) was set equal to the initial stiffness (K_{max}), and (2) the predicted stiffness did not exceed the initial stiffness.

2.4 GPR Applied Shear and Stiffness Predictions

Figure 1 compares the GPR predictions of the applied shear and stiffness with their corresponding experimental value. Points lying on the 45-degree line represent zero-error predictions. Approximately 95% of the predictions had variances below 1.4, while the remaining points were labeled as high-variance predictions, indicating lower confidence. The ten-fold mean absolute percentage errors were 7% and 18% for applied shear and stiffness predictions, respectively. Although the stiffness prediction error was considered acceptable, the results exhibited noticeable scatter, suggesting that incorporating additional high-quality training data could improve prediction accuracy.

Figure 1. Normalized shear and stiffness obtained from testing and GPR.

3. PRE-TEST PREDICTIONS

A 20 ft long 30 in. deep Pennsylvania PA18/30 beam was designed to be tested under shear at the Structural Engineering and Earthquake Simulation Laboratory (SEESL) at University at Buffalo. The design of the test specimen is shown in Figure 2. The two sides of the beam along the length had different shear reinforcement amounts to constrain shear failure to one side and to collect crack width-load data from both ends.

Figure 2. Test beam specimen design.

3.1 Shear Strength Predictions

Shear strength was predicted using the 10th Edition of the AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications (AASHTO 2024), ACI 318-19 (ACI Committee 318 2019), and ACI 318-25 (ACI Committee 318 2025) as summarized in **Table 1**. The variations among these predictions are consistent with the uncertainties associated with shear behavior of concrete structures.

Table 1. Shear strength predictions of the design codes for the test specimen.

Prediction Method	Predicted Shear Strength
AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications	133 kips
ACI 318-25 Detailed method	170 kips
ACI 318-19 Simplified method	105 kips

4. BEAM TESTING

The beam was cast on November 12, 2025 and tested on March 12–13, 2026 using a 600 kip capacity

actuator.

Figure 3 shows the test setup and the beam after the last loading cycle. The 20 ft long beam was supported 3ft away from each end to avoid prestress transfer length and was loaded at midspan. Loading was applied cyclically to document transient and residual shear crack widths corresponding to increasing loading. Load-midspan displacement was obtained. Additional instrumentation included strain gages on stirrups, longitudinal top flange reinforcement, strands, and concrete. The beam resisted loads higher than the ones predicted by design codes despite cracking (**Table 1**) and the research team is currently processing the test results.

Figure 3. Test setup and specimen after the completion of the final loading cycle.

5. WEB-BASED EVALUATION TOOL

A web-based evaluation tool was developed to facilitate the implementation of the algorithms bridge owners, engineers and inspectors. The tool predicts the shear strength, applied shear, and stiffness for given beam properties and crack width as shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Web-based evaluation tool.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A web-based evaluation tool that used ML to predict shear strength, applied shear, and stiffness of PC beams was developed. This tool can support bridge owners in making repair decisions. The mean absolute percentage error were 7% and 18% for applied shear and stiffness predictions, respectively. A 30 in. deep I-beam was tested under cyclic shear and resisted shear higher than the ones predicted by design codes. Detailed measurements of crack widths, strains, and displacements were recorded during testing. The test results provide valuable data for validating ML predictions.

7. REFERENCES

- AASHTO (2024). AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications. Washington, DC, American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials.
- ACI Committee 318 (2019). Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318-19) and Commentary on Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318R-19). Farmington Hills, MI, American Concrete Institute.
- ACI Committee 318 (2025). Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318-25) and Commentary on Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318R-25). Farmington Hills, MI, American Concrete Institute.
- Bennett, E., and Debaiky, S. 1974. "High Strength Steel as Shear Reinforcement in Prestressed Concrete Beams." ACI SP-42 Shear in Reinforced Concrete, American Concrete Institute, 231-248.
- Bruce, R. N 1962. "An Experimental Study of the Action of Web Reinforcement in Prestressed Concrete Beams." Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- De Silva, S., and Witchukreangkrai, E. 2006. "Experimental study on shear cracking behavior in I-shaped partially prestressed concrete beams." Transactions of the Japan Concrete Institute, 28(2), 817-822.

- De Wilder, K., Lava, P., Debruyne, D., Wang, Y., De Roeck, G., and Vandewalle, L. 2015. "Experimental Investigation on the Shear Capacity of Prestressed Concrete Beams using Digital Image Correlation." *Engineering Structures*, 82, 82-92.
- Hanson, J. M., and Hulsbos, C. 1969. "Ultimate Shear Tests of Large Prestressed Concrete Bridge Beams." *ACI SP-26 Concrete Bridge Design*, American Concrete Institute, 523-549.
- Heckmann, C., and Bayrak, O. 2008. *Effects of Increasing the Allowable Compressive Stress at Release on the Shear Strength of Prestressed Concrete Girders*. FHWA/TX-09/0-5197-3. Austin, TX: Center for Transportation Research.
- Juszczak, P., D. Tax and R. P. Duin (2002). *Feature Scaling in Support Vector Data Description*. 8th Annual Conference of the Advanced School for Computing and Imaging, 19 Jun-21 Jun, Lochem – Delft, ASCI, Editors: Deprettere, E. F., Belloum, A., Heijnsdijk, J. W. J, van der Stappen, F.
- Lee, S.-C., Cho, J.-Y., and Oh, B.-H. 2010. "Shear Behavior of Large-Scale Post-Tensioned Girders with Small Shear Span-Depth Ratio." *ACI Structural Journal*, 107(2).
- Maruyama, K., and Rizkalla, S. H. 1988. "Shear Design Consideration for Pretensioned Prestressed Beams." *Structural Journal*, 85(5), 492-498.
- Moayer, M., and Regan, P. 1974. "Shear strength of prestressed and reinforced concrete T-beams." *ACI SP-42 Shear in Reinforced Concrete*, American Concrete Institute, 183-214.
- Teoh, B., Mansur, M., and Wee, T. 2002. "Behavior of High-Strength Concrete I-beams with Low Shear Reinforcement." *ACI Structural Journal*, 99(3), 299-307.
- Villamizar, S., Ramirez, J. A., and Aguilar, G. 2017. "Shear Strength and Behavior of High-Strength Concrete Prestressed Beams." *ACI Structural Journal*, 114(1).
- XuanI, X., Rizkalla, S. H., and Maruyama, K. 1988. "Effectiveness of Welded Wire Fabric as Shear Reinforcement in Pretensioned Prestressed Concrete T-Beams." *ACI Structural Journal*, 85(4).
- Wan, X. (2019). *Influence of feature scaling on convergence of gradient iterative algorithm*. *Journal of physics: Conference series*.

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